
Successful Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Treatment of Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS): A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is a gastrointestinal disorder in which human gut becomes more sensitive and the muscles of the digestive system have abnormal contractions that affect bowel movements. Though IBS cannot be cured as per the main stream medical science, it can be managed through an integrative and holistic approach such as Yoga Prana Vidya System, to minimize the effect IBS has on our overall health and quality of life, as observed in the case presented in this paper.

Methods: This paper uses a full depth case study method going through patient's medical history and records before and after healing, and also taking the feedback from the patient, and evaluating the present health status.

Results: Within 10 days of healing and following suggested Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) guidelines, the patient is able to do all the daily home activities, cook food, go for a walk, travel, better breathing, and practicing forgiveness sadhana which has become an important part of the routine. Her sleep cycle, energy levels are better now. She no longer has episodes of vomiting. The patient is able to eat food well and also has gained some weight which she lost earlier.

Conclusions: As an integrative and holistic system of treatment and healing, Yoga Prana Vidya System offers tools and techniques easy to follow and practice, for curing illnesses, and improving overall health and immunity. There is scope for more research to conduct with targeted studies to gain more knowledge about this type of gastrointestinal disorders.

KEYWORDS: Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS), Gastrointestinal disorders, Yoga Prana Vidya system ®, YPV ®,

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INTRODUCTION

Irritable Bowel Syndrome

Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is a group of symptoms that occur together, including repeated pain in your abdomen and changes in bowel movements, which may be diarrhea, constipation, or both. With IBS, one may have these symptoms without any visible signs of damage or disease in the digestive tract.[1].

While the exact cause of IBS, is unknown, studies have suggested that IBS might be related to a few specific changes in the body. Some symptoms may be caused by spasms, uncontrolled contractions in the muscles of the colon. The nerve endings in the intestines also may become unusually sensitive, magnifying pain. The reasons for these changes are

not always known, but factors that have been linked with IBS include bacterial overgrowth, use of antibiotics, and psychological factors such as stress, among others.[2].

Psychological factors: The brain and gut are closely connected such that our thoughts and emotions can trigger symptoms in the gut, and the health of our gut can shape our mental well-being. Stress can cause more contractions in the intestines and increase sensitivity. It is not yet established whether stress or other psychological factors may be a cause of IBS or vice versa. However, a 2017 study in the Journal of Neurogastroenterology and Motility found that people with IBS have higher levels of depression and anxiety compared with those who don't have the disorder. IBS also is more

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common among people who experienced psychological trauma as children.[2].

Antibiotics: There are trillions of bacteria in human digestive tract besides viruses, and fungi which collectively are termed as the gut microbiota or gut flora. These microorganisms play several critical roles in our health, including digestion and immune system function. When we take antibiotics to combat bacterial infections, the drugs also kill helpful bacteria in the gut. Some animal and human research suggests that this disruption could lead to IBS in some cases. The evidence is inconclusive and more research is needed. [2].

Bacterial overgrowth: Small intestinal bacterial overgrowth (SIBO) is a condition some people with IBS also have, which is a surplus of bacteria in the small intestines. There is no evidence to show whether SIBO can be a cause of IBS, but people with IBS are more likely than others to test positive for SIBO. In addition, some research has found that IBS symptoms often decrease after antibiotic treatment that focuses on bacteria in the small intestine. SIBO occurs when extra bacteria in the colon back up into the small intestine. In this situation, people often have symptoms typical of IBS such as bloating, constipation, abdominal pain, and diarrhoea. [1]

Managing IBS

The prevalence of IBS in general population of India is 15%, and most of the patients approach the general practitioner, and only 30%–50% of the workload at gastroenterology

outpatient clinics. There are very few community-based epidemiological studies on IBS in India [3]. There are several well-studied, nondrug, integrative approaches that can help to reduce IBS-related symptoms and restore a sense of control over one's life. [4]. Despite the prevalence of IBS, its diagnosis and management remain as challenges for global healthcare systems. [5]. Laird et al. [6] investigated and concluded that their meta-analyses have shown that psychotherapy improves gastrointestinal symptoms in adults with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS),

Yoga Prana Vidya System

Yoga Prana Vidya System is a no-touch and a no-drug energy healing modality which also works at a distance and can cure many physical or psychological problems. It is an integrated and a holistic system which promotes happiness and good health at physical, emotional and mental levels using breathing, healing techniques, meditation and yoga etc. In the healing techniques, the healer removes the diseased, dirty or the used-up energy from the affected part or the affected chakrams of the patient and fills it up with fresh energy. The main advantage of using Yoga Prana Vidya healing techniques is, firstly that the patient need not be physically present in front of the healer as the healing can be done from a distance, and secondly, it can cure many psychological ailments too which are emotional or mental in nature.

Fig 1: Energy body of a healthy person

Fig 2: Energy body of a sick person

Fig 3: Chakrams in the energy body

Fig 4: GDV camera Images of energy body

The energy body, also known as aura, of a being surrounds the physical body, and it consists of an inner aura, an outer aura and health rays connecting these two. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the energy body of a healthy person and sick person

respectively. The energy body consists of chakrams (see figure 3) and nadis for receiving and distributing the Pranic energy, also known as life force. Figure 4 shows the pictures of human aura taken using GDV (Gas Discharge

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Visualisation) camera before and after healing and correlates with images in figures 1 and 2 respectively. Yoga Prana Vidya system consists of self-practice modules such as physical exercises, Rhythmic yogic breathing, and meditation practices such as forgiveness sadhana and Planetary Peace Meditation. The healing process consists of several basic and advanced techniques of cleansing the chakrams and affected parts and energizing the same for desired results.

Published literature of over 35 articles shows that, by using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing techniques, many cases have been successfully treated such as, some difficult medical cases [7], Diabetes management & control [8], removing arterial block in heart without surgery [9], vision improvements for participants of an Eye Camp [10], improvements in holistic wellbeing and immunity of participants in a one-month YPV intensive programme [11], Role of Yoga Prana Vidya in first aid and emergency [12], improvements of health and immunity of senior citizens [13], speedy recovery of COVID patients [14], treatment of hypothyroidism [15], Lowering academic anxiety and enhancing academic performance of high school children [16], saving life of a snake-bitten human female [17], improvements in the cognitive abilities and social behaviour of mentally challenged children [18], managing the pain and side effects of a Hodgkin Lymphoma patient undergoing chemotherapy [19], healing treatment of a female patient suffering from kneecap dislocation [20]. A review of published literature shows some experimental studies also conducted with successful outcomes such as improvements in the wellbeing of prisoners [21], and significant reduction in anxiety and depression in corporate employees [22].

METHODOLOGY

This paper presents a case of chronic IBS of a human female patient, that was treated successfully using Yoga Prana Vidya system modalities as follows.

CASE REPORT

Patient Information

The patient is a 50 years aged housewife, resident of Panvel, Maharashtra.

Patient health history

1999- took heavy antibiotics for healing uterus infection due to retained placenta which later caused digestive issues (bloating after every meal, urgency to pass stool after every meal, hyperacidity)

2004- uterus infection that happened in 1999 caused severe swelling. For the swelling to heal and subside a course of heavy antibiotics was given. Which further led to jaundice.

The hospital in which she was first admitted denied that it was jaundice and gave different treatment, also refused to discharge as well. Somehow, she managed to shift to another hospital where treatment for jaundice was started. Her condition was very serious at that time, and was in hospital for about one month. Complete bed rest was given. Large

intestine and stomach were infected at that time. So, since then, she was advised to avoid certain foods (leafy veggies, sprouts, non veg)

2017 - slip disc after falling down the stairs (Started physiotherapy as family doctor advised not to take medicine because of health history)

2019 - started treatment for slip disc as there was no relief after physiotherapy sessions. Heavy medicines were prescribed. Since then, the episodes of distention, vomiting and diarrhea started.

2021 - lost 15 kgs over the period of 9 months as she wasn't able to eat due to pain in abdomen and vomiting after eating. She was not able to eat anything almost for 5 days in a week for about 9 months due to cramps, bloating, vomiting (10 to 12 vomits every day) and diarrhea. Even a sip of water would cause tremendous pain.

Pre - YPV medical conditions

Abdominal distention, persistent cramps along with continuous vomiting and diarrhea occurred at that time. With every few vomits distention and cramps would reduce a bit. She couldn't even drink water, with every sip of water the cramps would aggravate.

These episodes would happen after every 7 to 10 days and last up to 4 to 5 days. She was not able to eat any solid food. And over the time due to fear of vomits she ate very small quantity of food (half roti of rice, some sabzi / dhal, rice /fresh fruit juice/homemade soups). Besides these symptoms, there were no other co-morbidities.

Medical diagnosis of condition

At this stage, her Allopathy doctor said these were symptoms of IBS. For about 2 Months he prescribed some medicines which made her feel very sleepy. Doctor made it very clear that allopathy doesn't have any cure for this disease and he suggested to go for ayurveda or homeopathy.

The Medical reasons of losing 15 kgs weight were explained as - low food intake due to IBS. She was not able to eat solid food for about 9 months. She used to experience severe cramps in abdomen, vomiting and diarrhea, and hence, had liquid diet which led to weight loss.

Ypv Intervention details

Her daughter had attended the Ypv level 1 course from a YPV trainer on 12th December 2021. She felt intrigued by how light it felt just after practicing the simple protocols for cleansing. On 23rd December, 2021, she contacted the trainer for the healing of her mother's case. The trainer was physically staying at the YPV Ashram at that time attending a 15-day program. This trainer healed the patient distantly from 23rd December to 1st January 2022.

The duration for each healing was 35 mins daily, and the YPV Healing protocols used were, YPV Psychotherapy, and internal organ technique that was mainly focused on healing her abdominal pain, vomiting, bloating and energy loss. The healer used miraculous healing technique also for strengthening the patient's immune system.

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The patient was suggested to do Rhythmic Yogic breathing and forgiveness sadhana thrice in a day. It was noticed that the patient had a lot of emotional issues because of a sudden death of her mother in 2016 which was heartbreaking for her for which forgiveness helped her. It was also observed that the patient was doing breathing incorrectly until then, so by practicing YPV deep abdominal rhythmic breathing and proper guidance by her daughter and the healer, her breathing was corrected.

The progress of healings and results achieved are as given below.

Day 1 feedback – 23rd December 2021

The patient was able to sleep early around 12 midnight. Generally used to fall asleep around 3 am. Has some mild headache. Did the breathing exercise

Day 2 feedback – 24th December 2021

Patient was feeling much better now. After a long time, she slept like a baby. Her energy levels are better, and she's able to do household work after 12 months of complete bed rest.

Day 3- 25th December 2021 She's better than yesterday now, and is doing Kshama (forgiveness) sadhana and breathing thrice a day on her own. She also shared how light she feels after every kshama sadhana. Although she still has some pain in upper abdomen but it's much lesser than what it was earlier. Earlier due to pain she couldn't even do simple basic activities.

But now she has started walking, and constant fatigue and weaknesses is also not there. Earlier they literally used to force feed, now she feels hungry and asks for something to eat.

And, because she falls asleep early, she now wakes up early and is full of energy.

Day 4 - 26th December 2021 “*Kal raat se patient ko pain, cramps and bloating hai*” (Since last night, the patient has abdominal pain, cramps and bloating). This usually happens once every 10 days, but it is less this time.

Day 10- 1st January 2021 She's feeling really good. Her energy levels are amazing now. From someone who used to have no energy to even talk more than a few minutes, to someone who's going for a walk, is an amazing change.

“Thank you so much for healings. Day after tomorrow she is also going for a small vacation which was unbelievable until the healings.”, (feedback from the patient's daughter.)

Present condition

She is now able to do all the daily activities, cook food, go for a walk, travel, breathing better, and practicing forgiveness sadhana has become an important part of the routine. Her sleep cycle, energy levels are better now. She no longer has episodes of vomiting. She began eating well and have gained some weight. She is still under homeopathy treatment as she experiences pain sometimes very rarely, say, once a month. According to the doctor this is stress and sleep related.

DISCUSSION

Despite the prevalence of IBS, its diagnosis and management remain as challenges for global healthcare systems. Moayyedi et al. [5] recommend use of Water-soluble fibre (e.g., psyllium) for initial management that has been shown to provide overall symptom relief in IBS. YPV diet protocols also recommend use of Sat Isabgol (Psyllium husk) first thing in the morning for all people including healthy people for ease in bowel management.

According to Laird et al [6], Thoughts, emotions, and behaviours are proposed to be bi-directionally related to gut physiology and symptom manifestations in IBS. Psychological and behavioural treatments can help patients with IBS control and reduce their pain and discomfort and are seen as ancillary to or augmenting medical treatments. A meta-analysis by Laird et al [6] have shown that psychotherapy improves gastrointestinal symptoms in adults with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS). This is comparable to the practice of YPV psychotherapy which is an essential part of YPV system protocols that helps people to maintain calmer state of thoughts and emotions. Thus, it is evident that these practices of YPV, besides energy healing of relevant chakras, have helped the patient in this case to manage IBS effectively and consistently.

CONCLUSIONS

As an integrative and holistic system, Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) uses proven practices for normalizing and managing a range of illnesses including IBS as described in this case study. Applications of YPV have found acceptance as complementary and alternative medicine for a wide range of illnesses with successful results, offering immense scope for further research.

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Conflicts of interest

None

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